

Title: Chronic Fungal Infection Accelerates Age Polyethism in Ants Without Altering Immune Response

Authors: Michał Kochanowski^{a,d*}, Anna Dubiec^b, Aleksander Juszcak^c, Igor Siedlecki^d, Piotr Ślipiński^b, Marta Wrzosek^d, Enikő Csata^{b,e#}, Magdalena Witek^{b#*}

Affiliations:

^aUniversity of Warsaw, Faculty of Biology, Institute of Evolutionary Biology, Żwirki i Wigury 101, 02-089 Warsaw, Poland

^bPolish Academy of Sciences, Museum and Institute of Zoology, Twarda 51/55, 00-818, Warsaw, Poland

^cUniversity of Warsaw, Inter-faculty Individual Studies in Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Center of New Technologies, Stefana Banacha 2C, 02-097, Warsaw, Poland

^dUniversity of Warsaw, Faculty of Biology, Botanic Garden, Aleje Ujazdowskie 4, 00-478, Warsaw, Poland

^eCentre de Recherches sur la Cognition Animale (CRCA), Centre de Biologie Intégrative (CBI), Université de Toulouse, CNRS, 31062 Toulouse, France

[#]These authors contributed equally

Correspondence:

*Corresponding author: mj.kochanowski@uw.edu.pl, mwitek@miiz.waw.pl

Word count: 5953 (without title page, references and supplementary materials)

Highlights

1. Chronic fungal infection disrupts the division of labour in social insect colonies.
2. High fungal infection accelerated a switch from intranidal worker to forager.
3. Immune response correlated with workers' age, but not with performed tasks.
4. The higher the parasite load, the stronger the individual immune response.

Foraging is a critical activity for many animals, where individuals face many environmental pressures. Among these, parasite infection is one of the most negative threats, especially in social insects, where parasites can be shared among nestmates inside the nest, and can affect colony functioning by altering the division of labour within a colony. In the ant *Myrmica scabrinodis*, the ectoparasite fungus *Rickia wasmannii* infects the majority of workers in the colony and is linked to reduced lifespan, enhanced immune responses, and altered behaviour. Given that task allocation in *M. scabrinodis* is age-dependent, we tested whether *R. wasmannii* infection accelerates the transition to foraging due to the ants' shortened life expectancy. Our results confirmed that colonies with high infection intensity exhibited an earlier onset of foraging behaviour. Additionally, immune response, measured through phenoloxidase activity, was more strongly influenced by worker age than task switching or infection status, with older workers exhibiting higher immune activity. This suggests that while infection accelerates task switching, it does not directly impact immune function. Our findings highlight how chronic fungal infection can disrupt the division of labour in social insect colonies.

Keywords: ants, ectoparasite, fungal parasitism, division of labour, insect immunity, insect-fungi interactions, *Myrmica scabrinodis*, phenoloxidase system, *Rickia wasmannii*, task switch

The division of labour (DOL) is a fundamental trait of eusocial insects like ants, some bees and wasps, and termites (Wilson, 1971; Robinson, 1992). This organisational strategy allows for task specialisation and simultaneous execution, optimising the colony's ability to meet its needs and increase productivity (Duarte et al., 2012). In eusocial insects, task allocation is influenced by a range of factors, including morphological traits (Oster & Wilson, 1978), genetic predispositions (Stuart & Page, 1991; Robinson, 1992; Smith et al., 2008), personality (Trigos-Peral et al., 2023) and age-related polyethism, where younger workers care for brood while older individuals undertake riskier activities (Oster & Wilson, 1978; Gordon, 1989; Hölldobler & Wilson, 1990). However, social insect colonies must maintain flexibility in task performance, enabling them to adapt to changes in demand by reallocating workers to different tasks as needed (Calabi & Traniello, 1989; Robinson et al., 2009).

This flexibility is shaped by various internal and external factors, including colony demographics (e.g. depletion of honeybee workers, Huang & Robinson, 1996), environmental stressors (e.g. cold shock, Ulgezen et al., 2024), nutrition (Dussutour et al., 2016; Bernadou et al., 2020), worker longevity (Woyciechowski & Kozłowski, 1998; Morón et al., 2008; Tofilski, 2009), and parasitic infections (Bos et al., 2012; Lecocq et al., 2016; Natsopoulou et al., 2016; Li et al., 2023). In particular, parasitism can have severe consequences for colonies, reducing survival (Csata et al., 2014; Finnerty et al., 2018), increasing energetic demands (Mayack & Naug, 2009), and disrupting DOL by altering the timing of task transitions. Tasks performed in the nest are safer than foraging (Schmid-Hempel & Schmid-Hempel 1984; Visscher & Dukas 1997), and the latter is

typically performed by older workers or workers with shorter life expectancy (Woyciechowski & Kozłowski, 1998; Moroń et al., 2008). As infection increases the mortality rate of workers (e.g. Csata et al., 2014), this can lead to the selection favouring workers that begin foraging earlier in their lifespan. For example, the microsporidian parasite, *Nosema ceranae*, has been shown to accelerate the transition from intranidal tasks to foraging in honeybees (Lecocq et al., 2016; Natsopoulou et al., 2016), while carpenter ants (*Camponotus aethiops*) infected with a generalist insect pathogenic fungus (*Metarhizium brunneum*) stopped brood care and spent most of their time outside the nest (Bos et al., 2012).

Such disruptions are particularly notable when workers transition from intranidal tasks to foraging. Once they leave the nest, foraging workers are exposed to different parasites and pathogens, increasing the risk of infection. This heightened exposure is reflected in individual immune responses and broader colony-level immune investments, as workers must balance the demands of task performance with the need for immune defence (Schmid-Hempel, 1998; Evans & Pettis, 2005). At the individual level, task-related immune responses have been observed in various eusocial insects. For instance, in *Cataglyphis velox* ants, foragers exhibit heightened immune responses compared to nest-based nurses (Bocher et al., 2007). However, this observation contrasts with evolutionary theories of ageing, which predict that foragers would invest less in immune function due to their higher extrinsic mortality risks (de Verges & Nehring, 2016). This prediction was demonstrated in *Bombus terrestris* bumblebees, where foragers show lower immune responses than non-foragers (Doums & Schmid-Hempel, 2000). A recent study on paper wasps has shown that immune responses are more closely tied to the tasks individuals perform within the colony, rather than their age (Prato et al., 2024). This raises an intriguing question of whether similar task-related variation in immune function occurs in other eusocial insects, particularly in ants with age-related task specialisation.

Our study addresses two main questions: (1) Does fungal parasitism influence ants' non-reproductive division of labour? and (2) Which factor—age or task switching (transition from nest-bound tasks to foraging)—has a stronger impact on the immune response? We hypothesise that (1) fungal infection will accelerate task switching and (2) task switching, rather than age, will affect immune responses more significantly. To test these hypotheses, we conducted a behavioural experiment using *Myrmica scabrinodis* ants from colonies infected with the parasitic fungus *Rickia wasmannii* and parasite-free colonies. *R. wasmannii* is a superficial, mild parasite that affects entire colonies (Markó et al., 2016). Several studies have explored the effects of this ectoparasite on the physiology, morphology, and behaviour of its host ant, *Myrmica scabrinodis*. Research has shown that ants from infected colonies have smaller body sizes (Csősz et al., 2021), increased grooming behaviour (Csata et al., 2014), reduced aggressiveness and boldness (Csata et al., 2017a; Báthori et al., 2017), lower survival rates (Csata et al., 2014), as well as prolonged worker water consumption (Báthori et al., 2015). The *Myrmica* genus is characterised by age-related polyethism (Weir, 1958), making these ants an ideal model for studying the effects of parasitism on task switching. While it has been shown that immune responses are different between old and young *Myrmica* ants (Orbán-Bakk et al., 2024), the relative contribution of age versus task switching (intranidal vs foraging) in shaping immune function remains unclear. To disentangle which of these two factors has a main contribution to the response of the immune system, we measured immune response via phenoloxidase activity in workers of the same and known age but performing different activities like intranidal tasks or foraging roles.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study System: Host Ant and Fungal Parasite

The host ant, *Myrmica scabrinodis*, is a widely distributed Holarctic species that prefers moderately humid and open environments (Radchenko & Elmes, 2010). Its nests provide favourable habitats for various organisms (Thomas & Settele, 2004), including the ectoparasitic fungus *Rickia wasmannii* (Espadaler & Santamaria, 2012, **Figure 1**). This fungus lives superficially on the ant's cuticle without penetrating its tissues (Tragust et al., 2016). Unlike most fungi, it does not produce a mycelium. Instead, its body – called a thallus (plural: thalli) – consists primarily of a perithecium, which contains asci bearing sticky, two-celled spores that are transmitted between hosts through direct contact (Weir and Beakes, 1995). At sites where *Rickia wasmannii* is present, around half of *Myrmica scabrinodis* colonies are infected (Markó et al., 2016). Once established within a colony, the infection spreads rapidly and extensively, often infecting nearly all workers. Fungal colonization occurs throughout the ant body, though the head and abdomen are most heavily infected (Haelewaters et al., 2019). The intensity of infection is age-dependent, with older ants having more thalli than young ones (Markó et al., 2016).

Sample Collection

A total of 20 *Myrmica scabrinodis* colonies were selected and collected from a single meadow near Cracow, Poland (50.026780, 19.863400) in May 2022. Ten colonies were infected with *Rickia wasmannii*, while the remaining ten were uninfected. Ant species identification and fungal infection assessment were initially performed in the field and later confirmed in the laboratory using a Nikon SMZ 800 stereomicroscope. Ant species identification followed the key of Czechowski et al. (2002). After collection, ant colonies were transported to the laboratory in sealed plastic bags. The number of workers, queens, gynes, males and broods were counted for each colony (for demographic data, see **Table S1**). Ants were fed three times per week with an agar-based diet (Bhatkar & Whitcomb, 1970) modified by Dussutour & Simpson (2008).

Mother Nests

In the laboratory, colonies collected from the field, hereafter referred to as “mother colonies”, were housed in ventilated plastic boxes ($15 \times 23 \times 6$ cm) filled with plaster (**Figure S1 (a)**) and maintained at room temperature under a 10-hour light: 14-hour dark cycle. Mother colonies were monitored weekly for the presence of pupae, which were transferred to a temporal nest upon detection. Out of 20 mother colonies, 16 produced sufficient numbers of developing pupae to establish experimental nests (see below for details).

Temporal Nests

In total, 16 temporal nests were established (7 uninfected, 9 infected), each corresponding to a mother colony. Temporal nests were housed in ventilated plastic boxes ($15 \times 10 \times 5$ cm) filled with plaster (**Figure S1 (b)**). Each nest setup consisted of 120 workers and all available pupae from the mother colony. Each group consisted of 80 older (dark-red) and 40 younger (yellowish) individuals, as age differentiation in *Myrmica* spp. is based on cuticle pigmentation, which darkens with age (Cammaerts-Tricot, 1974; Moroń et al., 2008; Csata et al., 2017b). Temporal nests were checked daily for newly hatched workers, which were transferred to a Petri dish (90 mm diameter) with a piece of damp sponge cloth. Workers emerging over four consecutive days were grouped into the same age cohort. Ants were marked individually on the thorax and abdomen with a unique combination of colours using Art Deco enamel paint markers (Edding 751). Marking was performed at 5 to 6 days of age, once the cuticle had sufficiently hardened. After marking, ants were transferred to the experimental nests. These ants of known age are referred to as “experimental” in the text.

Experimental Nests

Experimental nests were designed to observe the task switching of experimental individuals. A total of 33 experimental nests were established: 15 with *R. wasmannii*-infected ants and 18 with uninfected ants. Each experimental nest consisted of a nest chamber and a foraging arena. The nest chamber was a square plastic box ($12 \times 12 \times 8$ cm) filled with plaster, featuring a round cavity (\varnothing 60 mm and 8 mm deep) in the middle, referred to as the "brood chamber." A 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube (without the lid) filled with water and closed with cotton was placed inside the brood chamber, which was covered with red foil. The nest chamber was connected to the foraging arena via a 15 cm long silicone tube (\varnothing 8 mm). Foraging arenas were plastic boxes ($9 \times 5 \times 4$ cm) with walls coated with Fluon to prevent ants from escaping (**Figure S1 (c)**). Ants had continuous access to the foraging arenas, where food was replaced three times per week.

At the start of the experiment, each experimental nest was established with 30 old workers, 15 young workers, and 15 larvae taken from the mother and temporal nests to develop a stable social environment. Experimental workers were systematically transferred from their temporal nests to the experimental nests after hatching and marking. Each experimental nest received up to 24 experimental workers. If more than 24 experimental workers emerged from a single mother colony, an additional experimental nest was established for that colony.

Behavioural Assay

We monitored the task switching of experimental workers over 64 days, involving a total of 569 workers (323 uninfected and 246 infected) across the 33 experimental colonies. Behavioural observations were made once or twice daily, with a minimum of six-hour intervals between observations, and scheduled at least one hour after feeding. Additionally, daily counts of dead workers were also recorded and once per week dead workers were replaced by new ones taken from the mother colony. During observations, experimental

workers were categorised into two groups: (1) inside the nest chamber, or (2) in the foraging arena. The experimental workers observed at least three times in the foraging arena were classified as foragers and subsequently used in immunological assays. To compare immune responses among workers of the same age performing different tasks, an intranidal worker from the same age cohort and from the same experimental colony was sampled alongside each forager. The workers were frozen at -80°C . Haemolymph was extracted from the workers within a week of their freezing, and further immunological analyses were conducted once the behavioural experiment had been completed. All specimens used in the experiment were deposited in the entomological collection of the Museum and Institute of Zoology, PAS, Warsaw.

Immune Function Assay

To assess whether ants of the same age cohort performing different tasks exhibit differences in immune response, we measured the activity of the phenoloxidase (PO) system. We used two complementary methods to assess phenoloxidase activity. The first measured the active form of phenoloxidase in the insect's haemolymph (hereafter referred to as PO). The second involved artificially activating the precursor enzyme prophenoloxidase (Laughton & Siva-Jothy, 2011) and measuring the combined levels of the active enzyme and its precursor, representing the potential immune activity that could be mobilised (hereafter referred to as PPO). PO and PPO activities were quantified using the protocol of Orbán-Bakk et al. (2024). A total of 216 samples were analysed, with the sample size for each studied group detailed in **Table S2**.

We used homogenates of headless ant bodies to measure PO and PPO activity, as accurately sampling specific volumes of haemolymph from such small organisms is challenging (see Castella et al., 2010). The heads were retained for further size

measurements. For haemolymph extraction, the headless ant bodies were placed in Eppendorf tubes containing 60 μ l of cold sodium cacodylate/ CaCl_2 buffer (0.01 M Na-Cac, 0.005 M CaCl_2). The bodies were crushed 15 times, vortexed for 1 minute, and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 4°C at 6600 rpm. The supernatant was then transferred to a new Eppendorf tube. Throughout the procedure, the tubes were kept on ice. The extracted haemolymph was stored at -80°C until further analysis and was isolated within 7 days of freezing the ants.

The colourimetric reaction was prepared in a 96-microwell plate with a flat bottom (Greiner Bio-One, reference number: 655101), with all preparation steps performed on ice. To minimise procedural variation, samples for PO and PPO analyses from the same individuals were placed in adjacent rows. Additionally, to account for potential inter-plate variation, each combination of colony infection status \times performed task was represented on every plate. For the PO and PPO assays, 35 μ l and 30 μ l of distilled water were added to the designated wells, along with 10 μ l of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to maintain a constant pH. Frozen haemolymph-buffer samples were thawed on ice for 5 min., briefly vortexed, and centrifuged for 5 min. at 6600 rpm at 4°C. Then, 20 μ l of the mixture per well from each individual was transferred to the respective wells for PO and PPO assays.

We activated prophenoloxidase by adding 5 μ l of chymotrypsin (reconstituted in 1 mM HCl containing 2 mM CaCl_2 , following the manufacturer's recommendations) to measure PPO levels. The plate was then removed from the ice for 5 minutes, and the contents of the wells were subjected to gentle mixing to initiate the reaction. After this, the plate was returned to the ice, and 35 μ l of L-dopamine substrate (L-DOPA, at a concentration of 4 mg/ml in distilled water) was added to trigger the reaction. During this process, L-DOPA was converted into dopachrome. The increase in optical density due to dopachrome formation is directly proportional to the enzyme quantity (Söderhall & Cerenius, 1998). Immediately after adding L-DOPA, the plate was placed in a prewarmed UV-vis spectrophotometer (Synergy

HT, BioTek Instruments, Inc., Winooski, Vermont, USA) to measure the absorbance at 490 nm. The colourimetric reaction, performed at 30°C, was monitored for 400 reads, taken every 15 seconds. To account for naturally occurring changes in mixture colour, each plate contained triplicate control reactions for PO and PPO assays. These controls included all assay reagents except for the haemolymph-sodium cacodylate buffer mix, which was replaced with sodium cacodylate buffer. Enzyme activity was determined based on the slope of the linear phase of the reaction (V_{max} , Wilson et al., 2018). We used PO Calc Software (Kohlmeier et al., 2015) with the following settings: number of values prior – 5, number of values after – 45, threshold – 7.5, number of data points prior – 10, number of data points post – 25, and minimum number of data points – 25. Data points were eliminated if the absorbance curve was too irregular.

Since the immune assays were performed using haemolymph extracted from homogenates of the thorax and abdomen, we controlled for this variation in haemolymph volume using the body size index of individual ants. Specifically, immune measures were normalised by dividing individual immune values by the standardised head size, calculated as the individual's head surface area divided by all workers' mean head surface area (Castella et al., 2010).

Morphometric and Parasite Infection Measures

Head morphometric measurements were conducted on a subset of experimental workers sampled for immunological assays. Head width was measured below the compound eyes, and head length was measured from the most anterior part of the clypeus to the posterior cephalic margin in a full-face view (see McMullan & Brown, 2006; Orbán-Bakk et al., 2022). Measurements were taken using a Nikon ECLIPSE Ni light microscope at $\times 40$ magnification,

with NIS Elements 5.11.00 D software. The head surface area was calculated by multiplying the head width by the head length.

To quantify infection intensity at a colony level, we counted all fungal thalli on the heads of 20 randomly selected foragers from each infected mother colony. Thalli counting was performed using a Nikon SMZ 800 stereomicroscope at $\times 40$ magnification (see Markó et al., 2016; Csata et al., 2017b). Colony infection level was determined by calculating the average thalli per worker head. In all analyses and results where the level of infection is mentioned, we considered the level of infection at the colony level, not at the individual level.

Data Analysis and Visualisation

To examine whether infection influences the task switch from intranidal worker to forager, we performed a Cox Regression Mixed Models using the *'coxme'* function from the *'coxme'* package (Therneau, 2024). We run the Cox Regression Mixed Models twice, first with the infection presence, and second with colony-level infection intensity on the subset of workers from infected colonies. We included the mother colony tag as a random factor to account for dependencies. Infection intensity was quantified as the total number of *R.wasmannii* thalli per individual at the colony level (mother colony) and analyzed as a continuous variable in all statistical models to preserve the full range of infection data and maximize statistical power. For visualization purposes only, we applied a 25-thalli threshold to categorize infection levels in figures, following established protocols for Laboulbeniales infections in ants (Konrad et al., 2015; Báthori et al., 2015). To visualise the effect of infection intensity on task switching, we plotted the predicted cumulative probability of switching tasks across different levels of infection, based on a Cox proportional hazards model. To analyze whether infection influences mortality rate, we used Cox Regression Mixed Models (*'coxme'* function from the

'*coxme*' package; Therneau, 2024) with mother colony identification number as a random factor.

To investigate the effects of infection presence and intensity, worker age (days after hatching), and task specialisation (intranidal or forager) on standardised PO and PPO activity, we performed two linear mixed models (LMM, one for PO and one for PPO). To account for dependencies, we included the identity of the experimental nest nested within the identity of the mother colony as a random factor in each model. Model selection was performed using Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC), with models having $\Delta AICc \leq 2$ considered for selection (see Burnham & Anderson, 2002).

To test the effects of *Rickia wasmannii* infection on worker mortality and body size (head width \times head length), we used linear mixed-effects models with mother colony identity as a random effect. For each response variable, we first assessed the effect of infection presence by comparing a full model that included infection status as a fixed effect to a corresponding null model using likelihood ratio tests fitted with maximum likelihood. To further explore the role of infection intensity, we repeated these analyses using only workers from infected colonies, with infection intensity as a fixed effect compared against respective null models.

All statistical analyses were performed using R (v4.1.2, RCoreTeam, 2021) and RStudio (v2022.12.0). Data were tested for normality assumptions. Model quality was assessed using residual diagnostics provided by the '*DHARMA*' package (Hartig, 2024), including checks for deviations from expected distributions, dispersion, and outliers, and residual plots against predicted values. For model-based analysis, we used the '*lme4*' package (Bates et al., 2015). Automated model selection was performed using the '*dredge*' function, and model averaging was conducted with the '*model.avg*' function in the '*MuMIn*' package (Bartoń, 2024). Collinearity among explanatory variables was checked using Variance

Inflation Factors (VIF), calculated with the *'vif'* function from the *'car'* package (Fox & Weisberg, 2019). Effect size (Cohen's d value) was calculated using the *'effectsize'* package with the *'effectsize'* function (Ben-Shachar et al., 2020). Spearman correlation (*'cor.test'* function) was used to assess the overall correlation between standardised PO and PPO activity. Figures were generated using the *'ggplot2'* package (Wickham, 2016).

Ethical Note

The study was conducted in Poland, where no legal regulations govern the collection and maintenance of *Myrmica scabrinodis* colonies in laboratory conditions. This study adhered to the ASAB/ABS Guidelines for using animals in research. As ants, including the study subject *Myrmica scabrinodis*, are invertebrates not protected by law, no special permissions were required for experimentation. Nevertheless, all ants were handled with care throughout the experiments. When inspecting colonies for infected ants, efforts were made to minimise disruption and disturbance to their natural environment. Additionally, **Table S1** in the supplementary materials details the number of collected individuals.

RESULTS

Effect of Infection on Mortality, Task Switching and Worker Size

Over the 64-day experimental period, neither infection presence ($p = 0.565$) nor infection intensity ($p = 0.666$) significantly affected worker mortality. We observed a transition from intranidal tasks to foraging in 111 out of 568 experimental workers (20.04%), comprising 62 (19.87%) uninfected and 49 (20.25%) infected individuals. The colony infection status did not significantly affect the average age at which individuals switched tasks (Coxme: $n = 111$, $z = 0.09$, $P = 0.93$). However, the infection intensity within the infected colonies had a

significant impact: individuals from highly infected colonies switched to foraging significantly earlier (Coxme: $n = 49$, $z = 3.33$, $P = 0.001$; **Figure 2**).

We found that infection presence, among individuals sampled for immune assays, had a significant impact on worker head size ($\chi^2 = 5.61$, $P = 0.018$): uninfected ants had an average head size of approximately 0.985 mm^2 ($\pm 0.035 \text{ mm}^2$ SE), while infected ants showed a significant reduction in head size of 0.070 mm^2 ($\pm 0.030 \text{ mm}^2$ SE; $t = -2.375$). The random effect of colony accounted for considerable variation ($SD \approx 0.114 \text{ mm}^2$), suggesting that colony membership strongly influences head size.

Effect of Infection and Task Switching on Immune Response

We found a significant correlation between standardised immune measures (PO and PPO activity; Spearman rank correlation: $r_s = 0.49$, $P < 0.0001$). As a result, we excluded standardised PO as an explanatory variable from the PPO model. The best-supported PPO models included worker age, performed task (intranidal vs foraging), infection presence, and infection intensity of the mother colony (**Table 1**; for the best-fitted models, see **Table S3** in the supplementary materials). Standardised PPO levels were positively correlated with age ($\beta = 6.22 \times 10^{-5} \pm 4.91 \times 10^{-6}$, $z = 12.59$, $P < 0.001$; **Figure 3**). While performed task (intranidal vs foraging), infection presence, and infection intensity were retained in the best-fit model, none of these variables significantly correlated with standardised PPO levels (**Table 1**), though the effect size for PPO expression and colony infection status was medium-large (Cohen's $d = 0.79$). Our best-supported PO models included worker age, infection intensity, and infection presence (**Table 1**; for the best-fitted models, see **Table S3** in the supplementary materials). Standardised PO levels were positively correlated with worker age ($\beta = 3.77 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.19 \times 10^{-6}$, $z = 3.16$, $P = 0.0016$; **Figure 3**). While infection presence and

intensity were retained in the best-fitted model, they did not significantly correlate with standardised PO levels (**Table 1**).

DISCUSSION

Our results indicate that a high-intensity fungal infection accelerates the transition from intranidal tasks to foraging in *Myrmica scabrinodis* ants. These findings support the hypothesis that only the cumulative effect of parasite load significantly impacts colony fitness measured e.g. as worker survival (Báthori et al., 2015; Konrad et al., 2015). Additionally, both standardised PO (phenoloxidase) and PPO (prophenoloxidase) activity were associated with worker age but not with task switching from intranidal tasks to foraging.

Effect of Infection on Task Switch

We observed that the transition from intranidal tasks to foraging (task switch) occurred more quickly in colonies with higher infection intensity. This mirrors findings in honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) infected with the microsporidian fungus *Nosema ceranae*, accelerating age polyethism. *Nosema* infects bees through the digestive tract and can lead to high colony mortality (Natsopoulou et al., 2016; Lecocq et al., 2016). In contrast, nematode-infected clonal raider ants (*Ooceraea biroi*) tend to remain in the nest (Li et al., 2023), highlighting that the effects of parasitic infections on the task performance may vary on the host-pathogen system.

The rate at which social insect workers progress through tasks is often linked to longevity. Workers with shorter lifespans, typically due to injury or infection, tend to take on riskier tasks, like foraging, earlier than their healthier counterparts (Woyciechowski & Kozłowski, 1998; Moroń et al., 2008; Tofilski, 2009). Although, in our experiment we did not observe increased mortality in infected colonies this may be explained by our experimental

design: we immediately replaced any worker that died to maintain a balanced worker-to-brood ratio, potentially masking mortality effects that would be apparent in natural conditions. Several studies have shown that Laboulbeniales infections reduce ant survival (Csata et al., 2014; Báthori et al., 2015; Konrad et al., 2015), which may explain why workers in highly infected colonies begin foraging sooner than those in less infected or uninfected colonies.

Additionally, parasites may further increase host energetic stress through various mechanisms. They may directly exploit host resources or induce physiological (Yek et al., 2012; Dubovskiy et al., 2013; Konrad et al., 2015; Stoldt et al., 2021; Orbán-Bakk et al., 2022, 2024) or behavioural defences (Tragust et al., 2013; Csata et al., 2014). For example, honeybees infected with *Nosema ceranae* show increased energetic stress compared to healthy ones (Moret & Schmid-Hempel, 2000; Mayack & Naug, 2009). This heightened energy demand due to infection could help explain the accelerated task switch observed in highly infected *M. scabrinodis* colonies. Younger workers may begin foraging earlier to meet the colony's increased energetic needs.

Long-term parasitic infections can significantly deplete a colony's energetic resources, profoundly affecting both colony function and worker development. One potential response to mitigate this stress is the production of smaller workers, as they require fewer resources for development and maintenance (Peeters et al., 2017). This has been observed in *M. scabrinodis* colonies infected by *R. wasmannii*, where workers tend to be smaller (Csősz et al., 2021,) which is also supported by the results of our study, and possess thinner cuticles (Csata et al., 2018). Previous studies have shown that infected individuals have a shorter lifespan (Csata et al., 2014), which could lead to a reduction in the outside workforce. As a consequence, younger ants may be forced to take foraging tasks earlier, as observed in our study. However, the efficiency of this younger workforce remains an open question and

warrants further investigation. Given these uncertainties, our findings highlight that while infected colonies may attempt to compensate for resource depletion and workforce reduction by increasing foraging efforts, their overall ability to acquire resources may still be compromised. This increased activity aligns with a broader pattern observed in parasitised hosts, where agitation or hyperactivity is a common outcome of parasitic infections across various host-parasite systems (Cory & Myers, 2003; Biron et al., 2005; Hughes et al., 2011; Disney, 2012; Mayack et al., 2015). Such behaviours may enhance host mobility, potentially facilitating the spread of infections, particularly for external parasites. One straightforward explanation for this hyperactivity could be the mechanical stress or irritation caused by the parasite's presence, akin to ants becoming restless when foreign objects are attached to their bodies. These findings highlight the intricate interplay between infection, resource allocation, and task specialisation in social insect colonies.

It is important to notice that although we only observed individual positions (inside or outside the nest), this behaviour should be interpreted as foraging rather than social distancing for several reasons. We classified individuals as foragers only after observing them outside the nest on three separate occasions. In almost all cases, individuals returned to the nest after the first or second observation, suggesting they were visiting the foraging arena and returning to share food with nestmates. While Stroeymeyt et al. (2018) showed that social distancing can reduce pathogen transmission to vulnerable individuals (young nurses and queens), our experimental context differs. In our nests, the most valuable individuals were young workers and larvae, so we might expect infected older workers to spend more time outside. However, after collecting food, they are still going back to the nest. Detrain & Leclerc (2022) found that *Metarhizium*-infected *Myrmica rubra* workers did not show early spatial distancing when contagious, but only exhibited reduced mobility when moribund. Importantly, *Rickia wasmannii* infection does not reduce mobility in *M. scabrinodis* (Csata et

al., 2017b), and the longest-living colony member—the queen—is often most heavily infected (pers. observation). This suggests that social distancing from infected individuals would be maladaptive and lead to colony dysfunction. Therefore, the increased outside-nest activity we observed likely represents accelerated transition to foraging tasks rather than social distancing behaviour.

Effect of Infection on the Immune Response

Long-term parasite infections can have varied effects on colony members, potentially suppressing immune responses in some individuals while enhancing them in others (van Riet et al., 2007; Orbán-Bakk et al., 2022). Our findings revealed no significant differences in standardised PO or PPO levels based on infection presence and intensity, suggesting that colony-level parasitism did not impair the immune response of young workers. This aligns with Orbán-Bakk et al. (2024), who studied the same host-parasite system, at which only the relative worker age effect was checked, and reported no correlation between infection presence and PPO levels. However, our results for PO-level contrast with those of Orbán-Bakk et al. (2024) who found increased levels of PO in *M. scabrinodis* infected workers and with the work of Konrad et al. (2015), who demonstrated that *Lasius neglectus* workers infected with *Laboulbenia formicarum* showed increased expression of genes involved in the melanisation cascade, particularly in individuals with higher parasite loads. A key difference between these studies and ours is that they examined mature ants with fully developed infections, whereas, we focused on young workers in their first few weeks of life before substantial infection had developed. Given that infection presence and intensity were assessed at the colony level, our results suggest that colony-wide parasitism does not influence the immune system of individual workers at an early stage of their lives.

Age, Task Switch and Immune Response

Beyond infection status, our study aimed to determine whether immune responses in *Myrmica scabrinodis* are more strongly influenced by worker age or task switch. Over a 64-day observation period, we observed a consistent increase in standardised PO and PPO levels, with no significant differences between workers performing tasks inside the nest and foraging. This supports the hypothesis that PO activity is primarily age-dependent, as suggested by previous studies (Rolff, 2001; Adamo et al., 2006; Bocher et al., 2007; Schmid et al., 2008; Wilson-Rich et al., 2008; Armitage & Boomsma, 2010; Orbán-Bakk et al., 2022, 2024).

While task specialisation is often associated with ageing in social insects, only a few studies have directly compared the relative influence of age and task specialisation on immune responses in honeybees (Lourenço et al., 2019) and paper wasps (Prato et al., 2024) and to our knowledge results presented here are the first ones performed on ants. Lourenço et al. (2019) demonstrated that younger honeybee workers exhibit stronger immune responses, measured by the expression of an antimicrobial peptide gene, than older bees, highlighting the importance of age in shaping immunity. In contrast, Prato et al. (2024) found that task specialisation in paper wasps (*Polybia paulista*) had a greater impact on immunity, measured as encapsulation-melanization, than age. Foragers of *Polybia paulista* had higher immune responses than guards, regardless of age. However, foragers had similar immune responses to the nurses. These contrasting results, including the outcome of our study, suggest that the relative influence of age and task specialisation on immunity may vary depending on the species' biology and ecological and physiological contexts. Moreover, various immune responses were measured in the presented studies making the direct result comparison more difficult because of a trade-off between different immunological parameters (e.g. Otte et al., 2014), which may also be affected by age and task.

To sum up, our study on *Myrmica scabrinodis* provides insights into the complex interplay of parasitic infection, task switching, age and immune response. It supports the idea that the cumulative impact of *R. wasmannii* thalli can significantly affect colony dynamics as workers in highly infected colonies transition to foraging earlier. While our study focuses on individual-level responses to *Rickia* infection, the broader implications for colony fitness remain an important question for future research. Parasite-induced changes in division of labor could have cascading effects on colony performance, though the final outcome may depend on multiple factors. *R.wasmannii* infection might enhance colony resilience through increased behavioral flexibility, but also impose fitness costs through reduced efficiency in essential tasks like brood care and foraging. Future studies examining colony survival, reproductive success, and competitive ability in infected versus uninfected colonies would help clarify whether the individual-level changes we observed translate into meaningful fitness consequences at the colony level.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Michał Kochanowski: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing - original draft, **Anna Dubiec:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Methodology, **Aleksander Juszcak:** Investigation, **Igor Siedlecki:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - original draft, **Piotr Ślipiński:** Investigation, Writing - review & editing, Formal analysis, **Marta Wrzosek:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - review & editing, **Enikő Csata:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing - original draft, Supervision, Formal analysis, **Magdalena Witek:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Supervision, Writing - original draft

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is part of the project No. 2022/45/P/NZ8/04018 co-funded by the National Science Centre and the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 945339.

COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data and R scripts used for statistical analysis are available at the Github repository:
https://github.com/mjkochanowski/task_switch_Animal_Behaviour_2024

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE WRITING PROCESS

While preparing this work, the authors used chatGPT and DeepSeek to check and improve the readability and language. All content was subsequently reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final version of the publication.

REFERENCES

Adamo, S. A., & Parsons, N. M. (2006). The emergency life-history stage and immunity in the cricket, *Gryllus texensis*. *Animal Behaviour*, 72(1), 235–244.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2006.01.011>

Armitage, S. A. O., & Boomsma, J. J. (2010). The effects of age and social interactions on innate immunity in a leaf-cutting ant. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, *56*(7), 780–787.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2010.01.009>

Bartoń, K. (2024). MuMIn: Multi-Model Inference (R package version 1.48.4).

<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=MuMIn>

Bates, D., Mächler, M., Bolker, B., & Walker, S. (2015). Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *67*(1), 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>

Báthori, F., Csata, E., & Tartally, A. (2015). *Rickia wasmannii* increases the need for water in *Myrmica scabrinodis* (Ascomycota: Laboulbeniales; Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, *126*, 78–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2015.01.005>

Báthori, F., Rádai, Z., & Tartally, A. (2017). The effect of *Rickia wasmannii* (Ascomycota, Laboulbeniales) on the aggression and boldness of *Myrmica scabrinodis* (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Journal of Hymenoptera Research*, *58*, 41–52.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/jhr.58.13253>

Ben-Shachar, M., Lüdtke, D., & Makowski, D. (2020). effectsize: Estimation of effect size indices and standardized parameters. *Journal of Open Source Software*, *5*(56), 2815.

<https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.02815>

Bernadou, A., Hoffacker, E., Pable, J., & Heinze, J. (2020). Lipid content influences division of labour in a clonal ant. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, *223*(6), jeb219238.

<https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.219238>

Bhatkar, A., & Whitcomb, W. H. (1970). Artificial diet for rearing various species of ants.

The Florida Entomologist, *53*(4), 229–232. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3493193>

Biron, D. G., Marché, L., Ponton, F., Loxdale, H. D., Galéotti, N., Renault, L., Joly, C., & Thomas, F. (2005). Behavioural manipulation in a grasshopper harbouring hairworm: A proteomics approach. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 272(1577), 2117–2126. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2005.3213>

Bocher, A., Tirard, C., & Doums, C. (2007). Phenotypic plasticity of immune defence linked with foraging activity in the ant *Cataglyphis velox*. *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, 20(6), 2228–2234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1420-9101.2007.01424.x>

Bos, N., Lefèvre, T., Jensen, A. B., & D’Ettorre, P. (2012). Sick ants become unsociable. *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, 25(2), 342–351. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1420-9101.2011.02425.x>

Burnham, K. P., & Anderson, D. R. (2002). Advanced issues and deeper insights. In *Model selection and multimodel inference: A practical information-theoretic approach* (pp. 267–351). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-22456-5_6

Calabi, P., & Traniello, J. F. A. (1989). Behavioral flexibility in age castes of the ant *Pheidole dentata*. *Journal of Insect Behavior*, 2(5), 663–677. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01065785>

Cammaerts-Tricot, M. C. (1974). Production and perception of attractive pheromones by differently aged workers of *Myrmica rubra* (Hymenoptera Formicidae). *Insectes Sociaux*, 21(3), 235–248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02226916>

Castella, G., Christe, P., & Chapuisat, M. (2010). Covariation between colony social structure and immune defences of workers in the ant *Formica selysi*. *Insectes Sociaux*, 57(2), 233–238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-010-0076-3>

Cory, J. S., & Myers, J. H. (2003). The ecology and evolution of insect baculoviruses. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 34(1), 239–272.

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.34.011802.132402>

Csata, E., Bernadou, A., Rákósy-Tican, E., Heinze, J., & Markó, B. (2017b). The effects of fungal infection and physiological condition on the locomotory behaviour of the ant *Myrmica scabrinodis*. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 98, 167–172.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2017.01.004>

Csata, E., Erős, K., & Markó, B. (2014). Effects of the ectoparasitic fungus *Rickia wasmannii* on its ant host *Myrmica scabrinodis*: Changes in host mortality and behavior. *Insectes Sociaux*, 61(3), 247–252.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-014-0349-3>

Csata, E., Timuş, N., Witek, M., Casacci, L. P., Lucas, C., Bagnères, A.-G.,

Sztencel-Jabłonka, A., Barbero, F., Bonelli, S., Rákósy, L., & Markó, B. (2017a). Lock-picks: Fungal infection facilitates the intrusion of strangers into ant colonies. *Scientific Reports*,

7(1), 46323. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep46323>

Csata, E., Billen, J., Bernadou, A., Heinze, J., & Markó, B. (2018). Infection-related variation in cuticle thickness in the ant *Myrmica scabrinodis* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Insectes Sociaux*,

65(4), 503–506. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-018-0628-5>

Csősz, S., Rádai, Z., Tartally, A., Ballai, L. E., & Báthori, F. (2021). Ectoparasitic fungi

Rickia wasmannii infection is associated with smaller body size in *Myrmica* ants. *Scientific Reports*,

11(1), 14355. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-93583-0>

Czechowski, W., Radchenko, A., & Czechowska, W. (2002). *The ants (Hymenoptera,*

Formicidae) of Poland. Museum and Institute of Zoology PAS. ISBN 83-85192-98

Detrain, C., & Leclerc, J.-B. (2022). Spatial distancing by fungus-exposed *Myrmica* ants is prompted by sickness rather than contagiousness. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, *139*, 104384.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2022.104384>

de Verges, J., & Nehring, V. (2016). A critical look at proximate causes of social insect senescence: Damage accumulation or hyperfunction? *Current Opinion in Insect Science*, *16*,

69–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cois.2016.05.003>

Disney, H. (2012). *Scuttle flies: The Phoridae*. Springer Science & Business Media.

Doums, C., & Schmid-Hempel, P. (2000). Immunocompetence in workers of a social insect, *Bombus terrestris* L., in relation to foraging activity and parasitic infection. *Canadian*

Journal of Zoology, *78*(6), 1060–1066. <https://doi.org/10.1139/z00-035>

Duarte, A., Pen, I., Keller, L., & Weissing, F. J. (2012). Evolution of self-organized division of labor in a response threshold model. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, *66*(7),

947–957. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-012-1343-2>

Dubovskiy, I. M., Whitten, M. M. A., Kryukov, V. Y., Yaroslavtseva, O. N., Grizanova, E. V.,

Greig, C., Mukherjee, K., Vilcinskas, A., Mitkovets, P. V., Glupov, V. V., & Butt, T. M.

(2013). More than a colour change: Insect melanism, disease resistance and fecundity.

Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences, *280*(1763), 20130584.

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2013.0584>

Dussutour, A., & Simpson, S. J. (2008). Description of a simple synthetic diet for studying nutritional responses in ants. *Insectes Sociaux*, *55*(3), 329–333.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-008-1008-3>

Dussutour, A., Poissonnier, L. A., Buhl, C., & Simpson, S. J. (2016). Resistance to nutritional stress in ants: When being fat is advantageous. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, 219(6), 824–833. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.136234>

Espadaler, X., & Santamaria, S. (2012). Ecto- and endoparasitic fungi on ants from the Holarctic region. *Psyche: A Journal of Entomology*, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/168478>

Evans, J. D., & Pettis, J. S. (2005). Colony-level impacts of immune responsiveness in honey bees, *Apis mellifera*. *Evolution*, 59(10), 2270–2274. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0014-3820.2005.tb00935.x>

Finnerty, P. B., Shine, R., & Brown, G. P. (2018). The costs of parasite infection: Effects of removing lungworms on performance, growth and survival of free-ranging cane toads. *Functional Ecology*, 32(2), 402–415. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.12992>

Fox, J., & Weisberg, S. (2019). *An R companion to applied regression* (3rd ed.). Sage. <https://www.john-fox.ca/Companion/>

Gordon, D. M. (1989). Dynamics of task switching in harvester ants. *Animal Behaviour*, 38(2), 194–204. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-3472\(89\)80082-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-3472(89)80082-X)

Haelewaters, D., Boer, P., Báthori, F., Rádai, Z., Reboleira, A. S. P., Tartally, A., Pfliegler, W. P., De Kesel, A., & Nedvěd, O. (2019). Studies of Laboulbeniales on *Myrmica* ants (IV): Host-related diversity and thallus distribution patterns of *Rickia wasmannii*. *Parasite* 26, 29. <https://doi.org/10.1051/parasite/2019028>

Hartig, F. (2024). DHARMa: Residual diagnostics for hierarchical (multi-level/mixed) regression models (Version 0.4.7) [R package]. CRAN.

<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=DHARMa>

Hölldobler, B., & Wilson, E. O. (1990). *The ants*. Harvard University Press.

Huang, Z. Y., & Robinson, G. E. (1996). Regulation of honey bee division of labor by colony age demography. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, 39(3), 147–158.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s002650050276>

Hughes, D. P., Andersen, S. B., Hywel-Jones, N. L., Himaman, W., Billen, J., & Boomsma, J. J. (2011). Behavioral mechanisms and morphological symptoms of zombie ants dying from fungal infection. *BMC Ecology*, 11, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6785-11-13>

Kohlmeier, P., Dreyer, H., & Meunier, J. (2015). PO-CALC: A novel tool to correct common inconsistencies in the measurement of phenoloxidase activity. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 75, 80–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2015.02.015>

Konrad, M., Grasse, A. V., Tragust, S., & Cremer, S. (2015). Anti-pathogen protection versus survival costs mediated by an ectosymbiont in an ant host. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 282(1799). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2014.1976>

Laughton, A. M., & Siva-Jothy, M. T. (2011). A standardised protocol for measuring phenoloxidase and prophenoloxidase in the honey bee, *Apis mellifera*. *Apidologie*, 42(2), 140–149. <https://doi.org/10.1051/apido/2010046>

Lecocq, A., Jensen, A. B., Kryger, P., & Nieh, J. C. (2016). Parasite infection accelerates age polyethism in young honey bees. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 22042.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/srep22042>

Li, Z., Bhat, B., Frank, E. T., Oliveira-Honorato, T., Azuma, F., Bachmann, V., Parker, D. J., Schmitt, T., Economo, E. P., & Ulrich, Y. (2023). Behavioural individuality determines infection risk in clonal ant colonies. *Nature Communications*, *14*(1), 5233.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-40983-7>

Lourenço, A. P., Martins, J. R., Torres, F. A. S., Mackert, A., Aguiar, L. R., Hartfelder, K., Bitondi, M. M. G., & Simões, Z. L. P. (2019). Immunosenescence in honey bees (*Apis mellifera* L.) is caused by intrinsic senescence and behavioral physiology. *Experimental Gerontology*, *119*, 174–183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exger.2019.02.005>

Markó, B., Csata, E., Erős, K., Németh, E., Czemes, Z., & Rózsa, L. (2016). Distribution of the myrmecoparasitic fungus *Rickia wasmannii* (Ascomycota: Laboulbeniales) across colonies, individuals, and body parts of *Myrmica scabrinodis*. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, *136*, 74–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2016.03.008>

Mayack, C., Natsopoulou, M. E., & McMahon, D. P. (2015). *Nosema ceranae* alters a highly conserved hormonal stress pathway in honey bees. *Insect Molecular Biology*, *24*(6), 662–670. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imb.12190>

Mayack, C., & Naug, D. (2009). Energetic stress in the honey bee *Apis mellifera* from *Nosema ceranae* infection. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, *100*(3), 185–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2008.12.001>

McMullan, J. B., & Brown, M. J. F. (2006). The influence of small-cell brood combs on the morphometry of honey bees (*Apis mellifera*). *Apidologie*, *37*(6), 665–672. <https://doi.org/10.1051/apido:2006041>

Moret, Y., & Schmid-Hempel, P. (2000). Survival for immunity: The price of immune system activation for bumblebee workers. *Science*, *290*(5494), 1166–1168.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.290.5494.1166>

Moroń, D., Witek, M., & Woyciechowski, M. (2008). Division of labour among workers with different life expectancy in the ant *Myrmica scabrinodis*. *Animal Behaviour*, *75*(2), 345–350.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2007.06.005>

Natsopoulou, M. E., McMahon, D. P., & Paxton, R. J. (2016). Parasites modulate within-colony activity and accelerate the temporal polyethism schedule of a social insect, the honey bee. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, *70*(7), 1019–1031.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-015-2019-5>

Orbán-Bakk, K., Marczin, M. J., Gál, L., Heinze, J., Csata, E., & Markó, B. (2022). Under pressure: The effect of long-term fungal infection on the encapsulation response in ants.

Insectes Sociaux, *69*(4), 361–367. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-022-00879-z>

Orbán-Bakk, K., Witek, M., Dubiec, A., Heinze, J., Markó, B., & Csata, E. (2024). Infection with a non-lethal fungal parasite is associated with increased immune investment in the ant *Myrmica scabrinodis*. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, *202*, 108027.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jip.2023.108027>

Oster, G. F., & Wilson, E. O. (1978). *Caste and ecology in the social insects*. Princeton University Press.

Otti, O., Tragust, S., & Feldhaar, H. (2014). Unifying external and internal immune defences.

Trends in Ecology & Evolution, *29*(11), 625–634. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2014.09.002>

Peeters, C., Molet, M., Lin, C. C., & Billen, J. (2017). Evolution of cheaper workers in ants: A comparative study of exoskeleton thickness. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 121(3), 556–563. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biolinnea/blx011>

Prato, A., Santos, E. F., Ferreira, H. M., Oi, C. A., do Nascimento, F. S., Rantala, M. J., Krams, I., & de Souza, A. R. (2024). Immune response in paper wasp workers: Task matters more than age. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 154, 104629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2024.104629>

Radchenko, A., & Elmes, G. W. (2010). *Myrmica ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of the Old World*. Natura Optima Dux Foundation.

R Core Team. (2021). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.r-project.org/>

Robinson, E. J. H., Feinerman, O., & Franks, N. R. (2009). Flexible task allocation and the organization of work in ants. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 276(1677). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2009.1244>

Robinson, G. E. (1992). Regulation of division of labor in insect societies. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 37, 637–665. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.en.37.010192.003225>

Rolff, J. (2001). Effects of age and gender on immune function of dragonflies (*Odonata: Lestidae*) from a wild population. *Canadian Journal of Zoology*, 79(12), 2176–2180. <https://doi.org/10.1139/z01-190>

Schmid-Hempel, P., & Schmid-Hempel, R. (1984). Life duration and turnover of foragers in the ant *Cataglyphis bicolor* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Insectes Sociaux*, 31(1), 345–360.

Schmid-Hempel, P. (1998). *Parasites in social insects*. Princeton University Press. Schmid, M. R., Brockmann, A., Pirk, C. W., Stanley, D. W., & Tautz, J. (2008). Adult honeybees (*Apis mellifera* L.) abandon hemocytic, but not phenoloxidase-based immunity. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 54(2), 439–444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2007.11.002>

Smith, C. R., Toth, A. L., Suarez, A. V., & Robinson, G. E. (2008). Genetic and genomic analyses of the division of labour in insect societies. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 9(10), 735–748. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg2429>

Söderhäll, K., & Cerenius, L. (1998). Role of the prophenoloxidase-activating system in invertebrate immunity. *Current Opinion in Immunology*, 10(1), 23–28. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0952-7915\(98\)80026-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0952-7915(98)80026-5)

Stoldt, M., Klein, L., Beros, S., Butter, F., Jongepier, E., Feldmeyer, B., & Foitzik, S. (2021). Parasite presence induces gene expression changes in an ant host related to immunity and longevity. *Genes*, 12(1), 95. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12010095>

Stroeymeyt, N., Grasse, A. V., Crespi, A., Mersch, D. P., Cremer, S., & Keller, L. (2018). Social network plasticity decreases disease transmission in a eusocial insect. *Science*, 362(6417), 941–945. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat4793>

Stuart, R. J., & Page, R. E. (1991). Genetic component to division of labor among workers of a lepto thoracine ant. *Naturwissenschaften*, 78(8), 375–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01131406>

Therneau, T. M. (2024). coxme: Mixed effects Cox models (Version 2.2-20) [R package]. <https://cran.r-project.org/package=coxme>

Thomas, J. A., & Settele, J. (2004). Butterfly mimics of ants. *Nature*, 432(7015), 283–284.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/432283a>

Tofilski, A. (2009). Shorter-lived workers start foraging earlier. *Insectes Sociaux*, 56(4),

359–366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-009-0031-3>

Tragust, S., Mitteregger, B., Barone, V., Konrad, M., Ugelvig, L. V., & Cremer, S. (2013).

Ants disinfect fungus-exposed brood by oral uptake and spread of their poison. *Current*

Biology, 23(1), 76–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2012.11.034>

Tragust, S., Tartally, A., Espadaler, X., & Billen, J. (2016). Histopathology of Laboulbeniales

(Ascomycota: Laboulbeniales): ectoparasitic fungi on ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae).

Myrmecological News, 23, 81–89. https://doi.org/10.25849/myrmecol.news_023:081

Trigos-Peral, G., Maák, I. E., Ślipiński, P., & Witek, M. (2023). Behavioral and morphological

traits influencing variation in task performance of *Camponotus vagus* ants. *Insectes Sociaux*,

70(4), 451–461. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00040-023-00937-0>

Ulgezen, Z. N., van Dooremalen, C., & van Langevelde, F. (2024). Shift in distribution of

division of labour in chronically stressed honeybee colonies after perturbation. *Journal of*

Experimental Biology, 227(21), jeb247976. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.247976>

van Riet, E., Hartgers, F. C., & Yazdanbakhsh, M. (2007). Chronic helminth infections induce

immunomodulation: Consequences and mechanisms. *Immunobiology*, 212(6), 475–490.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imbio.2007.03.009>

Visscher, P. K., & Dukas, R. (1997). Survivorship of foraging honey bees. *Insectes Sociaux*,

44(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s000400050017>

Weir, J. S. (1958). Polyethism in workers of the ant *Myrmica*, part II. *Insectes Sociaux*, 5(3), 315–339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02223941>

Weir, A., & Beakes, G. (1995). An introduction to the Laboulbeniales: A fascinating group of entomogenous fungi. *Mycologist*, 9(1), 6–10. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-915X\(09\)80238-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-915X(09)80238-3)

Wickham, H. (2016). *ggplot2: Elegant graphics for data analysis* (2nd ed.). Springer-Verlag. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>

Wilson, E. O. (1971). *The insect societies*. Harvard University Press.

Wilson, K., Hofmann, A., Walker, J. M., & Clokie, S. (Eds.). (2018). *Wilson and Walker's principles and techniques of biochemistry and molecular biology* (8th ed.). Cambridge University Press.

Wilson-Rich, N., Dres, S. T., & Starks, P. T. (2008). The ontogeny of immunity: Development of innate immune strength in the honey bee (*Apis mellifera*). *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 54(10), 1392–1399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2008.07.016>

Woyciechowski, M., & Kozłowski, J. (1998). Division of labor by division of risk according to worker life expectancy in the honey bee (*Apis mellifera* L.). *Apidologie*, 29(1–2), 191–205. <https://doi.org/10.1051/apido:19980111>

Yek, S. H., Nash, D. R., Jensen, A. B., & Boomsma, J. J. (2012). Regulation and specificity of antifungal metapleural gland secretion in leaf-cutting ants. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *279*(1745), 4215–4222. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.1458>

Table 1. Results of the models of standardised PPO and PO activity

Model	β	SE	z	p
Standardised PPO				
(Intercept)	-1.14×10^{-3}	2.11×10^{-4}	5.37	<0.001
Age	6.22×10^{-5}	4.91×10^{-6}	12.59	<0.001
Task [Intranidal]	2.74×10^{-5}	8.29×10^{-5}	0.33	0.74
Infection Intensity	-1.89×10^{-7}	1.21×10^{-6}	0.20	0.84
Infection Presence [Present]	-9.55×10^{-6}	6.15×10^{-5}	0.16	0.88
Standardised PO				
(Intercept)	4.39×10^{-6}	5.05×10^{-5}	0.086	0.93
Age	3.77×10^{-6}	1.19×10^{-6}	3.16	0.0016
Infection Intensity	1.03×10^{-6}	8.60×10^{-7}	1.19	0.23
Infection Presence [Present]	-9.96×10^{-6}	2.64×10^{-5}	0.36	0.70

Table 1. Averaged models for standardised PPO (prophenoloxidase) and PO (phenoloxidase) activity in *Myrmica scabrinodis* workers infected with *Rickia wasmannii*. Estimates (β), standard errors (SE), z-values, and p-values are provided for each term. Significant terms ($P < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

Figure 1. Study objects. (a) A *Myrmica scabrinodis* worker infected with the ectoparasitic fungus *Rickia wasmannii*. The fungal thalli are visible on the ant body (photo by Daniel Sánchez García). (b) *Rickia wasmannii* thallus attached to the ant's cuticle (photo by Marta Wrzosek).

Figure 2. Foraging activity of *Myrmica scabrinodis* workers. The proportion of *M. scabrinodis* workers performing foraging tasks, categorised by infection intensity (divided into three levels) of *Rickia wasmannii*, plotted against worker age. We applied a 25-thalli threshold to categorize infection levels, following established protocols for Laboulbeniales infections in ants. The shaded areas represent the pointwise 95% confidence intervals for each corresponding function.

Figure 3. Age-dependent changes in immune functions. Relationship between standardised immune function (phenoloxidase system) and worker age in *M. scabrinodis* workers. The blue and orange lines indicate the regression lines, with grey areas showing the 95% confidence intervals.

Figure S1. Study design. The figure illustrates the three nest types used in the experiment. (a) **Mother nests** housed entire colonies collected from the field and were checked weekly for new pupae. (b) **Temporal nests** contained approximately 120 workers and pupae. They were designed to regulate the emergence of new workers, with separate Petri dishes used to isolate workers emerging over four consecutive days. (c) **Experimental nests** housed 45 non-experimental workers to establish the social context, along with up to 24 experimental workers. These nests were designed to monitor task-switching behaviour in experimental workers within the colonies and were inspected daily. The illustration was created with BioRender.com.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Table S1. Colonies demography data

Colony tag	Nr. of subnests	Nr. of sampled individuals	Infection status of the colonies	Infection level	Nr. of workers	Nr. of brood	Nr. of queens	Nr. of gynes	Nr. of males
1	4	16	uninfected	0	2399	373	1	126	0
2	1	14	infected	9.60	219	52	5	0	0
3	1	6	uninfected	0	340	69	1	0	0
4	2	18	infected	14.70	686	278	1	0	0
5	2	4	infected	7.60	1146	242	1	31	4
6	1	10	infected	6.50	1831	218	27	0	0
7	1	0	infected	20.78	1228	142	3	0	0
8	0	0	uninfected	0	1503	254	2	0	0
9	4	38	uninfected	0	1330	405	2	1	5
10	2	8	infected	13.65	479	282	1	0	0
11	0	0	infected	43.40	727	308	0	16	2
12	1	0	infected	10.05	1315	133	0	12	0
13	1	2	uninfected	0	1043	227	1	42	0
14	3	30	uninfected	0	1302	640	8	0	0
15	4	30	infected	16.10	337	308	28	0	0
16	0	0	uninfected	0	1183	344	1	0	0
17	1	0	uninfected	0	1638	719	4	0	1
18	4	28	uninfected	0	2448	659	9	0	0

Colony tag	Nr. of subnests	Nr. of sampled individuals	Infection status of the colonies	Infection level	Nr. of workers	Nr. of brood	Nr. of queens	Nr. of gynes	Nr. of males
1	4	16	uninfected	0	2399	373	1	126	0
2	1	14	infected	9.60	219	52	5	0	0
19	0	0	uninfected	0	1320	100	25	7	0
20	1	12	infected	42.05	971	454	1	0	8

Table S1. Detailed demographic data of the collected *Myrmica scabrinodis* colonies. The infection level of the colony was determined by calculating the average number of thalli per head based on 20 randomly sampled foragers per colony.

Table S2. Sample and Assay Numbers

Infection status	Nr. of foragers	Nr. of nurses	Sum
uninfected	62 / 55 / 48	58 / 52 / 44	120 / 107 / 92
infected	49 / 47 / 39	47 / 42 / 26	96 / 89 / 65

Table S2. Sample size of the studied ant groups. The first number in each cell indicates the number of sampled individuals, and the second and third numbers correspond to the number of successful determinations, PPO and PO, respectively.

Table S3. Model selection results

Model	df	logLik	AICc	Delta	Weight
Standardised PPO					
age + size	4	1083.244	-2158.3	0.00	0.243
age + size + task	5	1083.611	-2156.9	1.37	0.122
age + size + infection presence	5	1083.417	-2156.5	1.76	0.101
age + size + infection level	5	1083.384	-2156.5	1.83	0.098
Standardised PO					
age + infection level	4	1099.721	-2191.2	0.00	0.221
age + infection level + infection presence	5	1100.654	-2190.9	0.27	0.193
age + infection level + size	5	1100.115	-2189.8	1.35	0.113

Table S3. The best (delta AICc ≤ 2) LMM models explain the level of standardised PPO, and LM models explain the standardised PO activity in *M. scabrinodis* workers.